

Impact

Case Study

Investing in Women's Leadership in ELIXIR: Early Impact of the ELEAD Pilot Cohort

ELEAD (ELIXIR Leadership and Diversity mentoring programme) supports women's leadership growth across ELIXIR through structured mentorship, peer support and professional training.

By building confidence, visibility and career progression opportunities, ELEAD helps create a more inclusive and equitable research environment in STEM.

Overview

This report summarises the experiences of pilot cohort participants and explores how the ELEAD programme is contributing to leadership development across ELIXIR.

The experiences of Katharina F Heil, Mallory Freeberg, Laura Portell Silva and Maria Doyle provide illustrative examples of how ELEAD fosters personal growth and organisational benefit. While these stories represent a small sample of participants, they offer early evidence of outcomes that align with the programme's intended impact pathway.

Through structured leadership training, mentoring, and peer networks, participants develop confidence, reflective practices, and collaborative approaches that they actively apply in their roles.

The programme aims to have an impact at individual level but ultimately seeks a culture change within ELIXIR for fostering inclusive leadership in European Research Infrastructures – something Mallory Freeberg wisely summarises in her case study:

“ELEAD is an investment in community leadership. By empowering individuals, it seeds networks of mentors, collaborators, and role models whose impact extends far beyond the cohorts. It's given me the tools and confidence to lead effectively and help others grow – strengthening both individual careers and the collective capacity of ELIXIR.”

The leadership gap ELEAD seeks to address

ELIXIR's internal snapshots (2022, 2024) show a **persistent gender imbalance across most senior, decision-making roles** (e.g. Heads of Node, Technical Coordinators), with men holding the majority of posts.

The notable exception is the Node Coordinator role, where women are comparatively over-represented. However, this role is frequently administrative/operational in nature and does not always confer equivalent authority over budgets, strategy or grants. The pattern suggests a concentration of women in coordination and "glue" roles (indispensable for all Nodes), with under-representation in positions that carry formal decision-making and visibility.

ELEAD was created to address this structural gap by providing women with targeted leadership development, mentoring and peer networks. By building confidence, sponsorship and cross-Node connections, ELEAD aims to broaden access to roles with strategic responsibility (at project, team or Node level) and influence – thereby strengthening both individual careers and ELIXIR's overall leadership capacity.

In 2022 and 2024, women were over-represented only among Node Coordinators; men dominated most ELIXIR roles with formal decision-rights.

Figure: percentage of men and women in centrally established leadership positions in ELIXIR from 2022 to 2024.

How ELEAD creates change

ELEAD's theory of change identifies several interconnected areas through which the programme shows early indicators of impact:

- **Human Capital.** Strengthened leadership pipelines. Participants gain confidence and take on new responsibilities, preparing them to guide teams and initiatives effectively. Talent is retained in ELIXIR.
- **Resource Uptake / Legacy:** Emerging culture shifts. Reflective and supportive leadership behaviours are beginning to influence team and organisational culture more broadly. The ELEAD concept is adopted by other networks.
- **Infrastructure / Research Efficiency:** Leadership training and reflective practices enable participants to enhance internal workflows, optimise resource use, and thus, support the long-term efficiency and sustainability of research operations.
- **Relationship Capital:** Enhanced collaboration across Nodes. Mentoring, peer networks and reflective practices foster trust, knowledge sharing and cross-Node collaboration.

Methodology

Scoring of evidence

The impact of ELEAD’s theory of change was examined through qualitative analysis of four participant stories from the pilot cohort. Each story was mapped against the four impact areas using a 1–3 scale to indicate the strength of evidence observed:

Table: impact scores by participant and impact area.

	Human Capital	Relationship Capital	Resource Uptake / Legacy	Infrastructure Research Efficiency
Katharina F Heil	2	2	1	1
Mallory Freeberg	3	3	3	2
Laura Portell	2	1	2	1
Maria Doyle	2	2	2	2

- **Score 1:** Some indirect evidence – there are hints or possible contributions, but not strongly documented.
- **Score 2:** Clear benefit – the participant’s story shows a tangible, meaningful impact.
- **Score 3:** Concrete evidence of direct impact – strong, demonstrable change that can be attributed to the participant’s engagement in ELEAD.

Diversity in leadership styles

Radar chart: illustrating self-assessed leadership styles by participants.

Each story also includes a radar chart illustrating the participant’s leadership style, based on self-assessment conducted during the programme. Six styles were assessed on a scale from 1–5:

- **People-first:** I prioritise supporting my team’s needs above my own.
- **Collaborative / Consensus-building:** I work to involve the team and reach decisions together.
- **Coaching / Mentoring:** – I focus on developing others through guidance and support
- **Task-focused:** – I prefer to set clear instructions and ensure tasks are completed efficiently.
- **Empowering:** – I encourage autonomy and allow others to take responsibility
- **Visionary / Strategic:** – I focus on long-term goals and direction, inspiring others toward a shared vision.

Katharina
E. Heil

Change in role: Shifted from task management to line management

Organisation: ELIXIR Hub

Cohort: Pilot

About Katharina

When Katharina Heil joined the pilot ELEAD cohort, she was already established in her role as Programme Manager for Communities and Training at the ELIXIR Hub. She was beginning to share task management responsibilities within her team and was also preparing for the personal transition into motherhood. With an eye to the future, she was motivated by the prospect of moving into more senior roles that would allow her to lead teams and develop her own leadership style.

The ELEAD experience

Katharina took part in every part of ELEAD: the workshops, one-to-one mentoring, and peer mentoring. Each offered something different, but together they provided space for reflection and growth.

The workshops, led by experienced trainers, encouraged her to look at familiar challenges from new perspectives, and they opened up conversations that are rarely addressed in a professional setting. Her mentoring sessions created a confidential space to share her own career journey, while also gaining insights that helped her put situations into context.

What she found most valuable, however, was the peer mentoring group. These sessions created a supportive environment where real-life scenarios could be explored collectively. Katharina recalls how helpful it was to hear her peers' stories and to look at her own challenges through different lenses. It was not only preparation for future situations, but also a reminder of the importance of solidarity in professional growth.

The impact

For Katharina, the programme reinforced her readiness to step more fully into management responsibilities. Since completing ELEAD, she has taken on line-management duties and feels more confident in supporting colleagues through difficult moments. She has also become more conscious of the positive influence she can bring to her immediate working environment.

“I keep sharing and consulting others around challenging situations/moments where I feel I need advice. I try to make a (positive) impact on the people I work with and manage.”

Equally important has been a shift in perspective. ELEAD helped her to recognise the value she contributes to collaborative projects, and gave her confidence in her own abilities. The relationships built through mentoring and peer support continue to serve as a network she can draw on, both for advice and encouragement.

Looking ahead

Katharina has since returned to ELEAD as a mentor, keen to share her experiences and to continue developing through reciprocal learning. She also sees the peer mentoring model as something worth extending beyond the programme, so that more colleagues can benefit from the same supportive approach.

Her advice to others

She encourages future participants to embrace the experience fully, even if it means stepping outside their comfort zone.

“By setting aside time for yourself and engaging in honest conversations, you invest in your future as a leader.” ■

Human Capital	Relationship Capital	Resource Uptake / Legacy	Infrastructure Research Efficiency
Developed confidence in leadership; applied reflective practices in mentoring and daily decision-making.	Built cross-Node relationships through peer mentoring and collaborative sessions; fostered trust and shared learning.		Applied leadership skills to improve team workflows and decision-making processes; indirect operational improvement.

Table: evidence of impact

Mallory Freeberg

Current role: Human Genomics Team Lead, EMBL-EBI

Previous role: Coordinator, European Genome-phenome Archive, EMBL-EBI

Node: EMBL-EBI

Cohort: Pilot

About Mallory

As Coordinator of the European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA) at EMBL-EBI, Mallory Freeberg was managing a large team and leading collaborations across Europe when she joined the ELEAD pilot. It was a role with significant responsibility, yet she often felt there was a gap between her contributions and how they were formally recognised. Much of her time was spent on operational management, leaving little space to focus on bigger-picture strategy.

“I knew I was contributing meaningfully to pan-European initiatives and was proud that my voice was being heard, but I also felt that my professional growth had reached a plateau. To take the next step, I needed more than just additional responsibilities. I needed a role - and the confidence - that would allow me to move from managing a scientific service to shaping the future direction of sensitive human data management for real-world applications.”

The ELEAD experience

Mallory engaged fully in ELEAD, taking part in the workshops, one-to-one mentoring, and peer mentoring. While all components were useful, it was peer mentoring that had the most lasting impact.

Her group brought together women who were at a similar stage in their careers and active in many of the same communities. This created an immediate sense of understanding. Conversations ranged from navigating daily challenges to thinking about long-term career direction. Mallory describes the group as a rare safe space where she could speak openly about uncertainties, test ideas, and receive both encouragement and constructive challenge.

“These relationships have become some of the most valuable in my professional network. I know I can reach out to these colleagues not only for advice but also for encouragement, and that sense of community has been one of the most valuable outcomes of the ELEAD experience.”

These connections continued after the programme ended, reinforced by regular encounters at project meetings and conferences. What began as structured peer mentoring has

evolved into an ongoing source of support, with colleagues who remain among the most trusted in her network.

The impact

During her time on ELEAD, Mallory successfully transitioned into a new faculty-level role as Human Genomics Team Lead at EMBL-EBI. This marked a shift from managing a single service to overseeing multiple services and teams, while also taking on a more strategic remit. Around the same time, she was invited to co-lead the GA4GH Implementation Forum, expanding her visibility on the international stage.

“I have grown from overseeing one service to managing five services, and from leading a team of 12 to multiple teams totalling 30 staff. For the first time, I am a named principal investigator on grants. This recognition and achievement marked a milestone I had been working towards.” ➤➤

Human Capital	Relationship Capital	Resource Uptake / Legacy	Infrastructure Research Efficiency
Gained confidence, transitioned into leadership role (talent retention), now shaping human genomics landscape and co-leading GA4GH Implementation Forum.	Built strong cross-Node and peer relationships, providing and receiving support in project proposals, strategic decisions and leadership challenges.	Implemented ELEAD peer mentoring model at EMBL-EBI for new Team Leads, creating a support network and extending ELEAD practices.	Applied leadership skills to improve team workflows and decision-making processes; indirect operational improvement.

Table: evidence of impact

Mallory credits her ELEAD mentor with helping her clarify what she wanted from her next role and encouraging her to take on leadership opportunities that she might otherwise have hesitated to pursue. Peer mentoring, meanwhile, helped her manage the transition into her expanded responsibilities, offering perspective at a time when the new role felt overwhelming.

Alongside these career developments, Mallory notes subtler but equally important changes. She feels more confident contributing in high-level discussions, more intentional in setting priorities, and better able to balance operational demands with strategic work.

Mallory has also joined the ELEAD 2.0 Programme as a mentor, giving back part of the confidence and knowledge that she has gained throughout her own experience.

“Before my own participation, I might have declined the request to become a mentor. But my experience with ELEAD – and the encouragement of my mentor, whom I greatly admire – convinced me that I had something valuable to offer. Mentoring has been one of the most rewarding ways to give back, and it reinforced just how much the programme has shaped me.”

Looking ahead

Mallory has returned to ELEAD as a mentor, convinced that sharing experiences is a vital way of sustaining leadership capacity across the community. She has also adapted the peer mentoring model within EMBL-EBI, establishing a support group for new Team Leads that now includes over a dozen colleagues. In this way, she is helping to embed the benefits of ELEAD more widely.

“By adapting ELEAD’s peer mentoring structure locally,

we are embedding its benefits more widely within EMBL-EBI.”

Looking forward, she hopes to continue building on these experiences, seeking out leadership opportunities both within ELIXIR and at the international level. For her, ELEAD’s influence is not limited to her own career: it is about contributing to a stronger, more connected leadership pipeline across the life sciences.

Her advice to others

Mallory encourages those considering ELEAD to see it as an opportunity for growth, whether as a mentee or a mentor. “It’s a space to reflect, experiment and learn alongside peers who understand the challenges of leadership”, she says. More than a development programme, she sees ELEAD as an investment in the people who will carry the community forward. As she puts it,

“Supporting ELEAD means supporting the people who will carry our community forward.” ■

About Laura

Before joining ELEAD, Laura Portell Silva was managing BSC's participation in several major European projects, including ELIXIR-CONVERGE, HealthyCloud, BY-COVID, Genomics Data Infrastructure (GDI), FAIRplus, and deCYPher. She was also a key contributor to proposal development for initiatives such as ELIXIR STEERS and EOSC EVERSE. Her role required coordinating complex collaborations and ensuring timely delivery across multiple projects – a demanding task that left little space for reflection or long-term leadership development.

The ELEAD experience

Through ELEAD, Laura participated in all components of the programme – workshops, one-to-one mentoring and peer mentoring. Each contributed to her growth in distinct ways.

“Through my mentor’s guidance, I learned a great deal and was encouraged to make decisions I had previously been hesitant about. The workshops provided valuable insights into what it takes to be a good leader, and in the peer-mentoring sessions I received thoughtful advice from peers.”

The impact

Following ELEAD, Laura was promoted from Research Engineer to Team Lead, taking on expanded responsibilities and a more strategic role at the BSC. Laura says,

“The programme helped me develop a clearer understanding of my strengths and values as a leader, which in turn

strengthened my confidence in leadership, improved my communication and decision-making skills, and enhanced my ability to support the growth and motivation of my team.”

Looking ahead

Laura sees ELEAD's influence as ongoing. The tools and self-awareness gained continue to shape how she approaches leadership and professional growth.

“ELEAD helped me become a more confident and self-aware leader. It also reinforced the importance of continuous learning, self-reflection, and collaboration, which I plan to carry forward as I take on new challenges.”

Her advice to others

Laura encourages anyone considering ELEAD to seize the opportunity:

“It’s a great programme that offers the space and guidance to grow both personally and professionally. You gain a deeper understanding of your leadership style, strengths and values – and you connect with inspiring peers who share similar ambitions.” ■

Laura Portell Silva

Current role: Research Digital Assets Management Team Lead, Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC)

Previous role: Research Engineer at BSC

Node: ELIXIR Spain

Cohort: Pilot

Human Capital	Relationship Capital	Resource Uptake / Legacy	Infrastructure Research Efficiency
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Promotion to Team Lead; stronger leadership confidence, clearer self-awareness of values and strengths.		Early application of ELEAD tools to leadership and team management; no formalised application yet.	

Table: evidence of impact

Maria Doyle

Current role: Programme Manager of Global Bioconductor Community Training and Engagement, University of Limerick

Previous role: Bioconductor Community Manager

Node: ELIXIR Ireland

Cohort: Pilot

About Maria

When Maria joined the ELEAD pilot, she was working as Bioconductor Community Manager and Training Coordinator for ELIXIR Ireland. Her role involved supporting a global community of software developers and users, coordinating training and building engagement internationally. Having recently returned to Europe from Australia, she was still establishing her network and was new to ELIXIR, while trying to feel confident in a leadership role that required balancing day-to-day delivery with long-term planning. Working in a global open-source environment meant collaborating across continents and time zones, which added complexity to building relationships and effective communication.

The ELEAD experience

Maria took part in all components of the programme. Workshops encouraged her to revisit familiar challenges with new perspectives, while mentoring sessions provided a confidential space to reflect on her career path and leadership approach.

Peer mentoring, however, became the most transformative element. It was a new concept for her and quickly proved powerful. Exploring real scenarios collectively, hearing peers' experiences and examining her own challenges through different lenses offered practical insights and renewed clarity.

“ELEAD gave me the confidence and tools to take on bigger responsibilities and think more strategically about how I lead.”

The impact

Maria describes ELEAD as having a “significant impact” on her leadership style and confidence. She has shifted from being task-focused to adopting a more coaching and empowering approach. The peer mentoring relationships broadened her perspective and strengthened a professional network she can draw upon for advice and collaboration. She now feels more intentional about how she builds relationships and supports autonomy within her teams.

By the end of the programme, Maria applied for – and secured – a more senior Programme Manager role with expanded responsibilities. She also co-wrote and won two international

grants totalling €730k. She credits ELEAD with helping her prepare for these steps, giving her confidence to embrace a more strategic remit.

“ELEAD reminded me that leadership is about enabling others, not just ticking off tasks.”

Peer mentoring was a particular highlight, showing her the value of shared experience and how learning from others' challenges could strengthen her own approach. Leading the Bioconductor community requires not just technical coordination but cultural sensitivity and inclusive practice – skills she feels ELEAD helped her strengthen.

Looking ahead

Maria expects that both the relationships and tools gained through ELEAD will continue to inform her leadership. She sees them as essential for building inclusive networks, mentoring others effectively and maintaining a European-level perspective as she works on projects. She hopes to give back by mentoring future participants and embedding peer-mentoring principles within Bioconductor and ELIXIR.

Her advice to others

“Do it!”, she says. For Maria, ELEAD offers a valuable opportunity to reflect, build confidence and connect with peers who understand you.

“An investment in yourself and in building a stronger, more connected community.” ■

Human Capital	Relationship Capital	Resource Uptake / Legacy	Infrastructure Research Efficiency
Shifted from task-focused to coaching and empowering; secured a more senior Programme Manager role and co-wrote two international grants (€730k).	Strengthened her professional network through peer mentoring; gained new perspectives and relationships beyond the end of the programme.	Early indications of applying ELEAD approaches in her work; intends to embed peer mentoring practices within Bioconductor and ELIXIR communities in the future.	Leadership style shift to improve communication and strategic planning within a global open-source community; indirect influence on efficiency.

Table: evidence of impact

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